

**TABIIY MATERIAL TURLARI, ULARDAN BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF
TEXNOLOGIYA TA'LIMI DASRLARIDA BUYUMLAR
TAYYORLASHNI O'RGATISHNING SHAKL VA METODIKASI**

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Umumtexnika fanlari va mexnat kafedrası o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: *Maqoladatabiiy material turlari, ulardan boshlang'ich sinif texnologiya ta'limi darslarida buyumlar tayyorlashni o'rgatishning shakl va metodikasini qo'llash bo'yicha ma'lumotlar berib o'tilgan..*

Kalitso'zlar: *Tabiiymateriallar, uzluksizlik, qiziqtiruv, taqdimot, amaliyot, natija.*

O'zbekiston tabiati nihoyatda xilma-xil va g'oyat go'zaldir. Bu o'lka rang-barang tabiiy resurslar, foydali qazilmalar, o'simliklar, qushlar, daraxtlar, gullarga boydir. Tabiatda ajoyib narsalar ko'p, faqat uni ko'z bilan kuzatish va ilg'ay ola bilish kerak.

Bu tabiiy boyliklardan sanoatda, qurilishda, turmushda foydalanish bilan bir qatorda mehnat darslarida ham xom-ashyo sifatida foydalanish mumkin. Texnologiya ta'limi darslarida:

- o'simlik gullarining yaproqlari, barglari, ildizlari, tanasi, shoxlaridan;
- meva, sabzavot va poliz ekinlarning urug'laridan;
- qushlar patlari, paxta chanog'i, baliq tangalari va qiltanoqlaridan;
- boshqoli ekin somonidan;
- qum, tuproq, shag'al va boshqa turli tabiiy materiallardan foydalanish uchun katta imkoniyatlar mavjud.

Bu texnologiya ta'limi darslarida turli topshiriqlarini bajarish jarayonidagi materiallarga bo'lgan ehtiyojlarini qondirish imkonini beradi.

Ilk maktab yoshidan boshlab o‘quvchilarda ona tabiatga qiziqish va muhabbatni, undagi go‘zallikni ko‘ra bilishni tarbiyalash juda muhim. Tabiiy materiallar bilan ishlash ularni tabiatni kuzatishga bo‘lgan qiziqishlarini oshiradi. Kuzatishlar esa badiiy ijodiy qobiliyatlarni, ijodkorlik g‘oyasini, tushunchalarning aniqligini uyg‘otadi.

Tabiiy materiallarni butun yil davomida to‘plash mumkin, chunki yilning har bir fasli o‘z xususiyatlariga egadir. Erta bahorda lola gulini, terak popugini, daraxt va butalarining yosh novdasini; yoz faslida har xil urug‘larni, rezavorlarni donalarini, turli gullarni; kuzda daraxtlarni xilma-xil barglarini, mevalarini va shu kabilarni to‘plash mumkin.

Mehnatga qiziqish va muhabbatni shakllantirish - bolalar tarbiya-sida asosiy masalalardan biridir. Boshlang‘ich sinf o‘quvchilarini turli xildagi mehnati (ijtimoiy-xo‘jalik, qo‘l mehnati, tabiat qo‘ynidagi) negizida qobiliyatini, shaxsiy iqtidorini ertaroq ochish, kelajakda esa kasbni to‘g‘ri tanlashi yotadi. Tabiiy materiallar bilan ishlash o‘z negizida o‘quvchini ona tabiat bilan yaqinlashuviga, unga tejamkorlik va mehribonlik munosabatda bo‘lish va birinchi mehnat ko‘nikmalarini shakllantirish kabi ulkan imkoniyatlariga egadir.

Tabiiy material – bolalar ijodiyotini rivojlantirish uchun asosiy tayanch hisoblanadi. O‘quvchilarni o‘yinchoq va buyumlar yasashda ulardan qanday foydalanishni o‘rgatish zarur. Shu maqsadda tabiiy materiallar burchagi tashkil etiladi. Tabiiy materiallar burchagini sinfxonasida, uyda tashkillashtirish mumkin.

Tabiiy materiallardan buyum va o‘yinchoqlarni tayyorlash –qiziqarli, oddiy bo‘lmagan va juda yoqimli mehnatdir.

Bola faoliyatida tabiiy materiallarning muhim o‘rin tutishiga Makarenko A.S. diqqatini qaratgan. U, materiallar (loy, yog‘och, qog‘oz va h.k.) inson faoliyatga yaqinligini, materiallardan nodir buyumlar va madaniyatni yaratish mumkinligini

aytib o‘tgan. O‘yinchoqlar va materiallarda nafaqat tasavvur, balki ulkan ijodiy fantaziya mavjudligini ta’kidlagan .

O‘quvchilar tabiatga ekskursiyalar vaqtida turli xil tabiiy materiallar masalan: yong‘oq, barglar, shoxchalarni, hovuz qirg‘og‘idan – chiroyli toshchalar, chag‘onoqlarni olib kelishadi. O‘quvchilar tabiiy materiallarni teradilar, ushlab ko‘radilar, o‘rganadilar. Bu esa materiallarning shaklini, rangini har birining xususiyatini eslab qolishga yordam beradi. Masalan, bolalar yong‘oqning yumaloqligini, jigarrang ekanligini, ustki qismi g‘adir-budur ekanligini bilib oladilar, cho‘chqa yong‘oq esa oval shaklda yaltiroq sariq-jigarrang, qo‘g‘a – silindr, yumshoq baxmalsimon, jigarrang bo‘lishini bilib oladilar.

Tabiat bilan bo‘lgan muloqat bolalarning tasavvurini kengaytiradi, diqqat bilan kuzatish qobiliyatini shakllantiradi, tabiiy materiallardan buyumlar yaratishda idrokning bir butunligini saqlaydi. Buyumlarni yasashda o‘quvchilar avval qiynalsalar, keyinchalik, uzluksiz mehnat natijasida bolaning qo‘llari o‘ziga ishonch, aniqlik kabi sifatlarga ega bo‘ladi va barmoqlari epchil harakat qiladi. Qo‘l mehnati sensomotrikaning rivojlanishiga – qo‘l va ko‘z ishining mutanosibligini, harakat kordinatsiyalarini mukammallashuvishga, harakatlarning aniqligi asta-sekinlik bilan ko‘nikmalar tizimi hosil bo‘ladi. “Qobiliyat va iqtidor manbalari ularning barmoq uchlaridadir. Barmoqlaridan, obrazli qilib aytganda, ingichka jilg‘a bo‘lib ijodiy fikr manbasini oziqlantiradi” – deb yozadi V.A. Suxomlinskiy .

Tabiiy materiallar bilan ishlash bolaning aqliy rivojlanishiga, tafakkuri va fikrlash qobiliyatining rivojlanishiga katta ta’sir qiladi. Tabiiy materialdan buyum tayyorlash jarayonini kuzatadigan bo‘lsak, boshida bolalar namunani ko‘rib chiqadilar, tuzilmasini tarkibini, tayyorlash usulini tahlil qiladilar; bu jarayonni o‘zlashtirgandan so‘ng ish murakkablashadi: Bolaga tayyorlanadigan o‘yinchoqning rasmi yoki foto surati ko‘rsatiladi va oxirida, ular topshiriq yoki o‘zining o‘ylagan fikri asosida buyumning yasaydilar.

O'yinchoqlarni tabiiy materiallardan tayyorlashning qiziqarliligi bolalarning diqqatini rivojlantiradi, uning mustahkamligini oshiradi. Erkin diqqat shakllanadi. Masalan, kuchukchani tayyorlashda bolalarga avval uning oyoqchalarini mahkamlash joylarini diqqat bilan ko'rib chiqib (ular simmetrik holda turishi past ham, baland ham bo'lmasligi, haqiqiyga o'xshashi kerak) teshiklarini belgilash, boshi va boshqa detallarini mahkamlash joylarini ko'rib chiqish tavsiya etiladi.

Tabiiy materialdan qilingan buyumlar ko'pincha bolalarning qiziquvchanligini qoniqtiradi. Bu mehnatda har doim yangilik, ijodiy izlanish, yanada yuqori natijalarga erishish imkoniyati bor. Tabiiy materiallardan o'yinchoqlar yasash mehnati bola shaxsining rivojlanishiga yordam beradi.

O'yinchoqni yasash oson ish emas. Uni yasashda noaniqlikga duch kelganda, u mustaqil ravshishda uni yechishga harakat qiladi. Ba'zan biron bir ishni yasash uchun kerakli o'lchamda to'ng'iz yong'og'ini (butur, shishka) tanlash, o'yinchoq qismlarini ulash yo'llarini amalga oshirish va h.k.

Kattalar yordami bilan bola omadsizlik sababini va ularni yengish yo'llarini o'rganadi. Shu asnoda unda maqsadga intilish, qattiyatlik, boshlangan ishni oxiriga yetkazish kabi sifatlar shakllanadi.

Ushbu mehnat turida o'z faoliyatini baholash va nazorat qilish sifatini shakllantirishning real imkoniyatlari bor.

Tabiiy materialdan o'yinchoq yasash mehnati individual va jamoaviy bo'lishi mumkin. Kattalar kabi bolalarga ham jamoaviy mehnat ulkan quvonch olib keladi. Bu yerda shunisi muhimki, bolalar jamoaviy mehnatning natijasini, foydasini tushunishlari kerak.

Jarayon bosqichlarini taqsimlay olishni, umumiy maqsadni hisobga olgan holda o'z faoliyatini rejalay olish qobiliyatini bolalarda shakllantirish uchun jamoaviy ishning turli shakllaridan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Jamoaviy mehnat bolalarda jamoalik, do'stona munosabat, o'zaro yordam, birodarlik

kurtaklarini shakllantiradi. Jamoaviy mehnatning natijalari, ayniqsa kattalar tomonidan quvvatlanib bolalarga qanot bag‘ishlaydi, ularni yangi buyumlar yasashga undaydi. Har bir ishga ko‘tarinki ruhda kirishadilar. Shunday ekan, tarbiya va ta‘lim jarayoni to‘g‘ri tashkil etilsa, tabiiy material bilan ishlash bolalarni barkamol o‘stirishda samarali vosita bo‘lib qoladi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI

1. Makarenko A.S. To‘plamlar, 4 tom. -380 b.
- 2.Sanaqulov X.R. “Boshlang‘ich sinflarda qog‘ozdan amaliy ishlar”. Metodik qo‘llanma. – T., TDPU,2004
- 3.Suxomlinskiy V.A. Serdse otdayu detyam. Kiyev. 1973. -258s.

**TYPES OF NATURAL MATERIALS, THE FORM AND METHODOLOGY
OF TEACHING THE PREPARATION OF ITEMS IN PRIMARY CLASS
TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION LESSONS**

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Annotation: *The article provides information on the application of the types of natural materials, the form and methodology of teaching the preparation of objects in the technology education classes of the primary class.*

Keywords: *Natural materials, continuity, interest, presentation, practice, result.*

The nature of Uzbekistan is extremely diverse and beautiful. This country is rich in various natural resources, minerals, plants, birds, trees, and flowers. There are many wonderful things in nature, you just need to be able to observe them with your eyes. These natural resources can be used as raw materials in industry, construction, and life as well as in labor classes. In technology education classes:

- leaves, leaves, roots, stems, branches of plant flowers;
- from the seeds of fruits, vegetables and pulse crops;
- from bird feathers, cotton wool, fish coins and acorns;
- from grain straw;
- there are great opportunities to use sand, soil, gravel and other natural materials.

This allows to meet the needs of materials in the process of performing various tasks in technology education classes.

From primary school age, it is very important to educate students to be interested in and love Mother Nature, to see the beauty in it. Working with natural materials increases their interest in observing nature. Observations awaken artistic creative abilities, the idea of creativity, clarity of concepts.

Natural materials can be collected throughout the year, because each season has its

own characteristics. In early spring, tulip flowers, poplar buds, young branches of trees and shrubs; in summer, various seeds, berries, various flowers; in the fall, you can collect different leaves, fruits, etc. from the trees.

Formation of interest and love for work is one of the main issues in children's education. Early development of primary school students' abilities, personal talents, and the right choice of profession in the future is based on various types of work (social-economic, manual labor, in the bosom of nature). Working with natural materials basically brings the student closer to mother nature, has great opportunities to treat her with economy and kindness, and to form the first labor skills.

Natural material is the main basis for the development of children's creativity. It is necessary to teach students how to use them in making toys and objects. For this purpose, a corner of natural materials is organized. A corner of natural materials can be organized in the classroom or at home.

Making items and toys from natural materials is an interesting, unusual and very pleasant work.

Makarenko A.S. says that natural materials play an important role in children's activities. He said that materials (clay, wood, paper, etc.) are close to human activity, and that rare objects and culture can be created from materials. He emphasized that toys and materials contain not only imagination, but also a huge creative fantasy.

Students bring various natural materials during nature excursions, for example: nuts, leaves, twigs, beautiful pebbles and pebbles from the shore of the pond. Pupils pick, hold and study natural materials. This helps to remember the shape, color and characteristics of each material. For example, children will learn that walnuts are round, brown, and have a bumpy top, while walnuts are oval-shaped, shiny yellow-brown, and the pulp is cylindrical, soft velvety, and brown. they will find out.

Communicating with nature expands children's imagination, develops the ability to

observe carefully, preserves the integrity of perception when creating objects from natural materials. If students have difficulty making things at first, later, as a result of continuous work, the child's hands will have such qualities as self-confidence, accuracy, and fingers will move dexterously. Manual work leads to the development of sensorimotor skills - the balance of hand and eye work, the improvement of movement coordination, the precision of movements, and a system of skills is gradually formed. "Sources of talent and talent are at their fingertips. From his fingers, figuratively speaking, he feeds the source of creative thought as a thin stream," writes V.A. Sukhomlinsky

Working with natural materials has a great impact on the child's mental development, thinking and thinking ability. If we observe the process of making an object from natural material, at the beginning, children look at the sample, analyze its structure, composition, and the method of preparation; after mastering this process, the work becomes more complicated: The child is shown a picture or photo of the toy to be made, and at the end, they make the item based on the task or their own idea.

The fun of making toys from natural materials develops children's attention and increases their strength. Free attention is formed. For example, when preparing a puppy, it is recommended that children carefully consider the places where the legs are attached (they should be symmetrical, neither low nor high, they should be similar to the real thing), mark the holes, and consider the places where the head and other details are attached. will be done.

Products made of natural materials often satisfy children's curiosity. In this work, there is always innovation, creative research, and the opportunity to achieve higher results. The work of making toys from natural materials helps the development of the child's personality.

Making a toy is not an easy task. When faced with uncertainty in its construction, it

tries to solve it in independent development. Sometimes it is necessary to choose the necessary size of pig nut (butur, shishka) to make some work, to make ways of connecting toy parts, etc.

With the help of adults, the child learns the reasons for failure and ways to overcome them. At the same time, qualities such as striving for a goal, perseverance, and finishing the work started are formed.

In this type of work, there are real opportunities to evaluate and control the quality of one's own work.

The work of making toys from natural material can be individual and collective. Teamwork brings great joy to children as well as adults. It is important here that children should understand the results and benefits of teamwork.

It is advisable to use different forms of teamwork to form children's ability to divide the stages of the process and plan their activities taking into account the common goal. Team work forms the buds of teamwork, friendship, mutual help and brotherhood in children. The results of team work, especially supported by adults, give wings to children and encourage them to make new things. They start every job with a high spirit. Therefore, if the upbringing and education process is organized correctly, working with natural materials will be an effective tool for the proper upbringing of children.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Makarenko A.S. Collections, 4 volumes. -380 p.
2. Sanakulov H.R. "Practical works from paper in primary classes". Methodical guide. - T., TDPU, 2004
3. Sukhomlinsky V.A. Serdse otdayu detyam. Kiev. 1973. -258p.